

Book Review

Shoji Imafuku, *The Rehabilitation System as Culture: The Spirit of "Altruism" That Accompanies Rehabilitation*

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1. Bibliographic Information and Introduction

This book consists of five chapters spanning 230 pages, structured as a prologue, Part I (Chapters 1–3), Part II (Chapters 4–5), along with multiple dialogues, roundtable discussions, and columns. It is an ambitious work that reexamines Japan's rehabilitation system¹ through the distinctive lens of "the institutionalization of altruism" (pp. 23–45), discussing its historical development and contemporary significance. This review evaluates the book from three perspectives: "novelty as institutional theory," "practical utility," and "verifiability of arguments (empirical grounding and evidence)."

2. Overview of the Structure and Content

The book is broadly divided into two parts. Part I, "'Altruism' and Accompaniment"² (pp. 23–129), delves into the philosophical and dialogical exploration of the human vision and ethical sensibility that underlie "altruism" and "accompaniment," prior to explaining the system itself. Chapters 1 and 2 in particular examine, from multiple angles, the conditions under which "altruism" arises in relationships with others, positioning this as the premise for the subsequent institutional analysis. Part II, "Creating a Community of Support" (pp. 133–230), addresses contemporary challenges and future prospects. Each chapter interweaves dialogue, institutional analysis, and historical reflection, creating a layered resonance among ideals, systems, and practice—demonstrating a level of completion that goes beyond a mere policy handbook, achieving the quality of a work in cultural theory and intellectual history.

(1) Part I: The Philosophy of "Altruism" and Accompaniment

In Chapter 1, a fundamental question—"What is altruism?"—is posed through a dialogue with political thinker Takeshi Nakajima.³ Nakajima argues that "altruism" is not an act of bestowing goodwill on others through one's own will, but rather "an experience in which the self is moved by the existence of the other" (Nakajima, 2021, Chapter 2). This perspective suggests that the practice of probation officers (hogoshi) constitutes not a vertical relationship of "supporter–supported," but a horizontal relationship grounded in "chance encounters." Imafuku states that "among probation officers, there is a sense that, had circumstances been different, they themselves might have committed crimes," and positions this as a "dative ethics."⁴ This represents a human understanding rooted in "other-power" (tariki) and "resonance" (kannō) that transcends the limits of the modern self, deeply excavating the ethical foundation of the probation officer system.

In Chapter 2, the psychological structure of "accompaniment" is analyzed through a dialogue with clinical psychologist Kaito Higashihata. Higashihata teaches that "the beginning of accompaniment lies in agonizing over one's inability to accompany," locating the essence of care in the attitude of accepting the "anguish of not being able to engage" (Higashihata, 2019, Chapter 2). Through this discussion, it becomes clear that the activities of probation officers constitute not "treatment" or "correction," but a practice of "building relationships while wavering together" with the subject. Furthermore, the complementarity of "care" and "therapy" as two forms of practice is shown, depicting the collaborative relationship between civilian care provided by Volunteer Probation Officers (VPOs) and specialist therapy provided by Professional Probation Officers (PPOs) (i.e., legal and psychological interventions).

This collaboration serves as an important psychological foundation supporting the ideal of public-private partnership.

Chapter 3 traces the philosophical foundations of rehabilitation through its institutional history—from the Meiji-era "ex-prisoner protection projects," through the wartime "Judicial Protection Commissioner System," to the current "Probation Officer System"—revealing the distinctive nature of an institution formed not by state initiative but by "citizens' moral spontaneity." The phrase "慈悲以為本、利他以為先" (Compassion as

the foundation, altruism as the priority)⁵—proclaimed by Mitsuo Setoyama, a former Minister of Justice—constitutes the ethical core of the entire book, and has been inherited by the present day, transcending religious and cultural contexts.

(2) Part II: Regional Co-existence and International Development

In Chapter 4, through a roundtable discussion with social welfare scholar Masaki Harada and criminal policy scholar Yuki Takahashi, rehabilitation is redefined as an integral part of a regional co-living society. A perspective is presented for bridging "support" in the welfare domain and "treatment" in the criminal justice domain, and for reconceiving those who have committed crimes as "members of the community." Harada argues that "recidivism prevention" is inherently another expression of "rebuilding one's life," and that society's capacity for inclusion is being tested. Probation officers are not mere supporters but exist as "community cheerleaders" who jointly sustain the lives of their charges; their practice has a structure continuous with the community-based integrated care system.

In Chapter 5, the distinctiveness of the probation officer system is discussed from the perspective of international comparison. In the United Kingdom and the United States, probation officers are embedded in the state apparatus as professionals, while the involvement of civilian volunteers is limited. By contrast, in Japan, the state and civilian sectors collaborate closely, with probation officers functioning as "the ethical foundation of local communities." Carol Lawson⁶ demonstrates that this system is internationally acclaimed, and evaluates Japan as having established a distinctive model of "public-private collaborative criminal policy." The fact that the term "HOGOSHI" is being introduced in international contexts and is gaining recognition as a symbol of volunteer-participatory criminal policy is profoundly significant as an international transmission of cultural value.

3. Relationship to Theoretical and Social Background

This book examines, against a backdrop of transformation in contemporary society's views of human nature and community, how an ethic of "altruism" can be institutionalized as public policy. Its central concerns can be organized along three dimensions.

(1) A Counter-Axis to Neoliberalism and the "Society of Isolation"

In contemporary Japan, the permeation of neoliberal policies since the 1980s has intensified a tendency for individuals to be held responsible for their own outcomes, while empathy and solidarity toward the socially vulnerable recede. As competitive principles have penetrated every domain and efficiency and results are prioritized, the imagination required to engage with others' difficulties has weakened, and isolation and exclusion have become normalized. Imafuku calls this structure "the institutionalization of egoism,"⁷ and proposes "the institutionalization of altruism" as the counter-concept. The probation officer system is emblematic of this, positioned as a mechanism for rebuilding social solidarity not through dependence on individual goodwill but through "institutional altruism." Standing at the intersection of state trust and regional ethics, the practice of probation officers represents a form of institutionalized empathy and points toward new possibilities for public life in contemporary society.

(2) Connection to the Regional Co-Living Society

Structural changes—an aging and declining birthrate, rural depopulation, and the increase in single-person households—have deepened isolation and support gaps within communities. In this context, the idea of a "regional co-living society" has attracted policy attention. This book accurately captures this trend and re-evaluates the probation officer system as a central mechanism for regional co-living. In particular, the theory of "accompaniment-type support"—whereby "continuing to stay connected is itself a form of support"—resonates deeply with the practice of probation officers. The "regional embeddedness" of probation officers—that is, the characteristic of providing support from within the community, within everyday relationships—is a cultural resource that sustains the sustainability of the system. This form of community-rooted support should be re-evaluated as a social practice that goes beyond mere volunteer activity and holds the key to the regeneration and inclusion of local society.

(3) Contrast with International Criminal Policy

From a global perspective, criminal policy has in recent years been reinforcing managerial and technocratic tendencies under the banner of "risk management" and "recidivism prevention." Particularly in Western nations, the execution of punishment has been quantified and standardized, and perspectives rooted in human relationships

and care are retreating. By contrast, Japan's rehabilitation system occupies a distinctive position as a "social healing model"⁸ supported by the cultural ethics of local communities. As Lawson points out, "HOGOSHI" is not simply civilian supplementation but a symbol of "culture-rooted criminal policy," with human-centered values animating the foundation of the system. Imafuku emphasizes this point and suggests the possibility that Japan's rehabilitation system could serve as a model for a "criminal policy of care" with international applicability. This is an attempt to re-evaluate the cultural foundations of the system and reaffirm its significance in a global context.

4. The Significance and Originality of the Author's Argument

The greatest originality of Imafuku's argument lies in repositioning the rehabilitation system as a "culture of altruism" and illuminating its institutional and ethical foundations from multiple angles. Chapter 3 in particular, "Reflecting on the Origins and Significance of the Probation Officer System" (pp. 109–129), concretely demonstrates that the sustainability of the system is supported by regional ethics—a point that constitutes an important contribution not found in previous research.⁹ Below, this significance is organized from three perspectives.

First, the book positions "altruism" not merely as an ethical virtue but as a principle of institutional design. The activities of probation officers are often described as "well-meaning volunteering," but Imafuku reconceives them as "a public practice shared by the state and local communities." That is, altruism is not confined to individual interiority but is embedded in society as an institution, functioning as a reproducible structure. This perspective demonstrates the potential of institutions to create human solidarity beyond religion and creed, and proposes a form of institutional ethics as a "secular religion"¹⁰ in contemporary society.

Second, the book offers a positive reevaluation of the "non-professional quality" of probation officers. In contemporary society, professionalization is advancing while non-expert practice tends to be undervalued. However, Imafuku argues that it is precisely the "non-professional quality" of probation officers that holds the key to building natural trust relationships with their charges. This is grounded in the recognition that "common social wisdom"—that is, ethical judgment rooted in everyday experience and common

sense cultivated within the local community—is the force that actually makes the system work. This perspective can also connect with the "life-subject" theory in social welfare studies and the "ethics of relationality"¹¹ in care practice, rediscovering the value of "non-professional quality" as a cultural resource that sustains the practical effectiveness of the system.

Third, the book offers concrete proposals regarding the future prospects of the system. The author frankly acknowledges the challenges facing the probation officer system—such as aging, regional disparities, and a shortage of practitioners—and advocates a transition from an administration-dependent model to a "community-development model." To achieve this, he argues, it is necessary to establish mechanisms that encourage the participation of younger generations, to spread awareness of rehabilitation in educational settings, and to build support networks utilizing digital technology. In particular, new models such as the civil servant probation officer system in Toshima Ward¹² attract attention as attempts to reconcile organizational support with individual practice. Imafuku frames such institutional reforms not merely as administrative responses but as "cultural movements," aiming at the maturation and ethical regeneration of society as a whole. Underlying this is a firm belief that "society matures through acts of support," reflecting a strong determination to reconstruct the ethical foundations of society through institutional reform.

The concept of "the institutionalization of altruism" that Imafuku presents is theoretically persuasive, but measuring how it actually functions and what social effects it produces is not easy. How much the support provided by probation officers contributes to preventing recidivism and facilitating social reintegration would require long-term and multifaceted empirical research, including follow-up surveys after the completion of probation supervision and correlation analyses between the degree of probation officer involvement and social reintegration rates. While this book has provided a new perspective of "the institutionalization of altruism," the future challenge will be to translate this ideal into measurable indicators and build a research framework for assessing the practical effectiveness of the system.

5. Critical Examination and Challenges

This book is not only conceptually excellent but also does not lose sight of the complex realities of the field. The author looks honestly not only at the ideal image of the system but also at the difficulties and limitations of practice, leaving space for the reader's own reflection. Below, four issues are presented as challenges for future system operation and practice.

The first is the challenge of the gap between ideals and reality. The collaboration between the judiciary and welfare discussed in Chapter 4 (pp. 133–161) is theoretically important, but the book presents no empirical data on the outcomes of specific collaborative cases or on how much recidivism rates or social reintegration rates have improved as a result. Empirical verification through future research is essential to determine the extent of the gap between the ideal of realizing a regional co-living society and the actual state of judicial-welfare collaboration. In the field of probation officer activities, the number of subjects facing complex difficulties—mental illness, intellectual disability, addiction, elderly people living alone—is increasing. In such situations, the goodwill of probation officers and community support alone have their limits, and the connection between institutional support and specialist knowledge becomes indispensable. As Imafuku himself notes, network collaboration with specialists at probation offices, community welfare professionals, and medical institutions is important, and system design that does not leave probation officers "isolated" is required. Furthermore, mental health support and burnout prevention for supporters themselves should be institutionally developed; building a "system to support those who support" is an urgent task (Ueda, 2010, Chapter 1).

The second challenge concerns the cultivation of practitioners and the succession of the system. As the aging of probation officers progresses, motivation and the reconstruction of social recognition are needed to encourage participation by younger generations. The civil servant probation officer system in Toshima Ward introduced in Chapter 4 (pp. 183–187) attracts attention as a new model that enables the coexistence of institutional support by local government and job responsibilities. However, the book presents no data on what outcomes this system has actually achieved, on the continuation rates of participating civil servants, on the quality of relationship-building with subjects, or on comparative data with the conventional probation officer system. In order to expand such pioneering initiatives nationwide, effect measurement as a pilot project and refinement of institutional design based on its

outcomes are required. Additionally, efforts to convey the appeal and social significance of the system are needed through the systematization of "rehabilitation education" at universities and vocational schools, community awareness-raising activities, and experiential programs for young people. For the probation officer system to take root as a "culture," the development of an educational and social environment in which the next generation of practitioners can appreciate its value firsthand is indispensable.

The third challenge concerns the universalization of the "culture of altruism" and its institutionalization. The author presents this concept in Chapter 1 (pp. 23–70) and positions it as the theoretical foundation of the rehabilitation system; but the word "altruism" is deeply rooted in a Japanese cultural context and is often understood emotionally or in a spiritually idealist manner. In order to embed this in social structures, it is necessary to institutionalize "altruism as a system" in a reproducible form within legal frameworks, educational policy, community welfare policy, and so on. The "public philosophy of altruism"¹³ that Imafuku presents provides a theoretical starting point, but going forward, deepening the theory through social-scientific verification and empirical research, and applying it to institutional design, are to be expected. Moreover, exploring through international comparative research how "criminal policy as culture" takes root in society and enables sustainable support is also important. Universalizing the ideal of altruism requires the reconciliation of cultural sensibility and institutional rationality.

The fourth challenge concerns the methodology of verifying the system's practical effectiveness. While the book clarifies the philosophical and cultural foundations of the rehabilitation system through dialogue and historical-institutional analysis, the presentation of concrete cases and episodes about how the practice of probation officers actually brings about change in the lives of subjects is limited. In future research, life-story research that traces the long-term involvement of probation officers with their charges, and ethnographic approaches that describe the process of support in detail, would be valuable. Since concepts such as "altruism" and "accompaniment" denote human endeavors that are difficult to quantify and standardize, the accumulation of qualitative research that carefully captures the narratives of those directly concerned and the practical wisdom of the field is indispensable.

In addition to the above challenges, the following three points should be noted as

research gaps revealed through this review. First, there is a shortage of empirical research on measuring the effectiveness of the probation officer system. Statistical analysis is needed—using variables such as degree of involvement, duration of support, and content of support—to determine what kind of impact probation officer involvement has on subjects' recidivism rates and social reintegration rates. Second, there is the need for evaluative research on pioneering initiatives such as those in Toshima Ward. For new models such as the civil servant probation officer system, comparative surveys before and after introduction and effect verification through interviews with participants are essential. Third, there is a methodological challenge regarding the measurability of the "culture of altruism." The development of a research framework that captures both the cultural dimensions and the practical effectiveness of the system through a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative research is to be anticipated.

6. Conclusion

The Rehabilitation System as Culture is a work of important contribution that integrates three layers—institutional theory, philosophical theory, and practical theory—and redefines rehabilitation as a "culture of altruism." Its true value lies not only in its conceptually elevated ideals but in its careful capture of the pulse of the field and its depiction of the power of the "people" who animate the system. The emotions, conflicts, and empathy of each individual probation officer working within the system are described with care, allowing the reader to see the "face" of the institution.

"Recovery" becomes possible only through the existence of others——this simple yet profound truth is excavated by Imafuku from both institutional theory and cultural theory. What becomes visible through the figure of the probation officer is the archetype of a society in which human beings support one another, and within it, the ethical possibilities of Japanese society are concentrated. An institution is not merely a mechanism but a culture nurtured within human relationships, and the probation officer system is its emblematic practice.

The future of rehabilitation is no longer solely a matter for legal administration; it is a theme bound up with the cultural maturation of regional society as a whole. In the face

of challenges such as aging, regional disparities, and a shortage of practitioners, ensuring the sustainability of the system¹⁴ requires both the reaffirmation of cultural values and the strengthening of institutional support. This book is a compass pointing toward that future and can be called a precious intellectual resource for causing the "spirit of altruism" to resonate as the fundamental tone of society.

Imafuku's pen does not merely critique the rigidity of institutions but depicts affirmatively the human endeavors that breathe life within them. This stance offers readers a perspective that frames institutional reform not merely as a technical challenge but as a cultural and ethical one. To conceive of the rehabilitation system as "culture" is to overlay the future of the system with the future of humanity itself, and within that lies an expanse of hope and possibility.

Notes

1. The volunteer probation officer system is a civilian cooperation scheme established under the Volunteer Probation Officers Act and the Offenders Rehabilitation Act, in which Volunteer Probation Officers (VPOs)—commissioned by the Minister of Justice—carry out rehabilitation-related activities in close collaboration with Professional Probation Officers (PPOs), who are state officials working under the jurisdiction of probation offices.
2. For the historical development of the rehabilitation system, see also Yuji Takenaka, "A Study on the Development of the Rehabilitation System" (Academic Report of Kyoto Prefectural University [Public Policy], 7, 2015, pp. 145–158).
3. Takeshi Nakajima is a professor at the Institute of Liberal Arts, Tokyo Institute of Technology (now Institute of Science Tokyo), specializing in the history of modern Japanese political thought, particularly conservative and religious thought. He reconsiders the philosophy of "altruism" from multiple perspectives including religion, ethics, and evolutionary biology, and explores the ethical foundations that transcend the divisions of contemporary society.
4. "Dative ethics" is a central concept in this book, positioned as a human understanding that transcends the modern self and is grounded in "other-power"

(tariki) and "resonance" (kannō). Through this concept, the book argues that the practice of probation officers is not merely "support" but a horizontal relationship in which the self is moved by the other.

5. Mitsuo Setoyama was a Minister of Justice during the Shōwa era who firmly established the foundations of the postwar rehabilitation system. Inheriting the civilian protection activities since the Meiji era, this phrase is cited as a historical basis for discussing the distinctiveness of the probation officer system, constituting the ethical and philosophical foundation of rehabilitation.
6. Carol Lawson is a professor at the Graduate Schools for Law and Politics, University of Tokyo. The author introduces Lawson's international evaluation of Japan's probation officer system in the context of comparative criminal policy, positioning it as an example illustrating the distinctiveness of Japan's system.
7. Imafuku critically conceives of the contemporary social situation—in which the penetration of neoliberalism has brought competitive principles and self-responsibility into even public domains, causing social solidarity to collapse—as "the institutionalization of egoism." By contrast, "the institutionalization of altruism" refers to attempts such as the probation officer system to embed empathy and solidarity toward others within social structures through institutional frameworks rather than individual goodwill; it is the central theory of this book, indicating new possibilities for public life in the contemporary era.
8. A concept used to explain the distinctiveness of Japan's rehabilitation system in the context of international criminal policy. In contrast to Western models centered on correction through punishment and risk management, its characteristic lies in aiming at the social reintegration of subjects and the repair of social solidarity itself through the ethical and cultural resources of local communities and the activities of civilian volunteers (probation officers).
9. In Chapter 3, "Reflecting on the Origins and Significance of the Probation Officer System," Imafuku positions the activities of probation officers as "the practice of institutionalized altruism" and discusses how the tradition of mutual aid (gojo/kyōjo) in Japan has been passed down within the rehabilitation system. This reviewer understands this perspective to be the core argument of the book—understanding the system not merely as a legal framework but as a cultural practice.
10. A concept indicating the author's sociological and philosophical perspective that institutions themselves, without relying on religious creed or transcendent

existence, perform the function of guaranteeing community solidarity and ethical practice. The "institutionalization of altruism" in the probation officer system is presented as its concrete example.

11. The "life-subject" theory is a philosophical current in social welfare that emphasizes not one-sided support by professionals but the subjectivity of the person receiving support (the "life-subject") and their everyday activities within the community. The "ethics of relationality" is a perspective in the ethical examination of care practice that emphasizes not norms or principles but the mutual and dynamic relationship itself between the caring and the cared-for; it provides an academic context for deeply understanding the accompaniment-type support of probation officers.
12. The civil servant probation officer system of Toshima Ward is a new initiative in which Toshima Ward entered into an agreement with the probation officer association, permitting ward employees to engage in rehabilitation activities as part of their official duties. As a measure against the aging of probation officers and the shortage of practitioners, it is a nationally rare pioneering model in which local government supports the expertise and flexibility of its employees and promotes probation officer activities under public responsibility. In this book it is highly evaluated as "an attempt to reconcile organizational support with individual practice."
13. The collective term for the author's ethical and public-philosophical inquiry presented in this book. A theoretical foundation for embedding "altruism"—exceeding individual goodwill—and responsiveness and consideration toward others into society as a sustainable public institution. It functions as the philosophical pillar supporting institutional reform.
14. According to Ministry of Justice statistics (<https://www.moj.go.jp/content/001439283.pdf>, retrieved December 12, 2025), the average age of probation officers exceeds 65, with those aged 60 and over comprising approximately 80% of the total. Moreover, there are large disparities in the sufficiency rates of probation officers between urban and rural areas, and in some regions the number continues to fall significantly below the required quota. The fact that participation by younger and working-age people is not increasing is considered the greatest challenge to the sustainability of the system.

References

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Translator's Note: This is an English translation of the original Japanese article published in *Bulletin of the Institute for Social and Cultural Studies*, No. 87, March 2026. The translation aims to make this research on Japan's volunteer probation officer system and the institutionalization of altruism accessible to an international audience, contributing to comparative discussions in criminal justice policy and rehabilitation studies.